

REFORMS IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the education system in Uzbekistan, and it is also noted that one of the main elements of policy in the implementation of democratic reforms, sustainable development of the economy and integration into the world community is the continuous education system.

Today, Uzbekistan has achieved great achievements in all areas in a historically short period of time. Our country is boldly walking on its path of strong development. In particular, under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Islam Karimov, special attention is being paid at the level of state policy to the education of the young generation and the formation of their worldview based on national and universal values. This can be confirmed by the following words of the Secretary General of the United Nations Organization, Ban Gu-Moon: Uzbekistan has made great progress in achieving the Millennium Development Goals, ensuring the rule of law, protecting human rights, motherhood and childhood, and improving the education system. entered into These successes are the result of sustainable and human-oriented socio-economic reforms. Therefore, it is necessary to interpret the reasons for such achievements in the inextricable connection with the ever-increasing worldview, political consciousness and level of our courageous and tenacious people who have seen a lot. President Islam Karimov said about this: "this is due to the fact that today they are a decisive force, who have mastered modern knowledge and skills, who think independently and in a new way, who are able to take responsibility for the future of our country. it is because we consider our young people to be our trust, our support and our support," he emphasized.

In Uzbekistan, reforms aimed at fundamental reform of the education system, raising the quality and content of education to a new level, creating a modern mechanism for training qualified personnel, and updating educational programs and literature are being implemented gradually and systematically. Annual expenditure on education in our country is 10-12 percent of GDP. This is almost 2 times more than the relevant recommendations of UNESCO on the amount of investments needed to be directed to education to ensure the sustainable development of the country, i.e. 6-7 percent³. Strengthening the material and technical base of higher educational institutions, improving the living conditions of students and the functioning of social and household facilities, beautifying the territories of higher educational institutions,

including the fundamental repair of student residences located in the "Yoshlik" student town in our capital. extensive works have been carried out.

The decision of the head of our state, adopted on May 20, 2011, "On the modernization of the material and technical base of higher education institutions and the fundamental improvement of the quality of training of specialists" is to organize the activities of higher education institutions at the level of world standards, to equip them with modern textbooks, o An important program is being implemented in the provision of teaching manuals and scientific laboratories. Currently, in the development of our country, not only for healthy, but also for children and adolescents with various disabilities, taking into account the level of their disabilities, there are types of education in the following directions: - special preschool education; - individual education at home; - integration groups at pre-school general education institutions; - speech therapy centers and integration classes at secondary schools; - integration groups in special vocational colleges. In these institutions, children who are blind, visually impaired, deaf and visually impaired, mentally retarded, retarded in mental development, impaired in the movement of the limbs, and have complex speech defects receive education. Education of children and adolescents in need of special support in our country, taking into account the types and degrees of their disabilities, 8 areas of special education (mentally retarded, retarded mental development, speech, vision and hearing impairments children) organized correctional education. If we look at the international level, in the next period, as a result of the democratization of education reforms and the fight against discrimination, the worldview of society changed, and a new approach was developed among people of different categories, that is, inclusive education projects. Therefore, in Article 41 of our Constitution, "Everyone has the right to education." Free general education is guaranteed by the state. School work is under state control. It is worth noting that the efforts made in the education system in Uzbekistan and the achieved results are also recognized by the international community. Of course, the Law "On Education" developed at the initiative of the head of our country, which is consistently implemented, the National Personnel Training Program, the State Nationwide Program for the Development of School Education and other important legal documents are examples of this.

This solid legal basis allows us to educate our future heirs based on modern standards, bring out their talent and bring them up healthy and well-rounded. Providing the young generation with modern education at the level of world requirements, introducing advanced teaching methods, establishing the activities of new educational institutions, in short, raising the growing young generation to adulthood is more important than today's reforms. is the ultimate goal in mind. In addition, training, retraining and increasing the experience of qualified professors and teachers, ultimately educating the young generation to be mature in all aspects, has become a vital necessity. In this sense, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted on June 12, 2015 "On measures to further improve the system of retraining and professional development of managers and pedagogues of higher education institutions" became extremely important in this regard. Because this decree aims to improve the quality of training of highly qualified specialists based on the continuous improvement of the professional level and qualification of professors and teachers of higher educational institutions in our country, and the introduction of an improved system of their regular retraining in accordance

with today's requirements. According to the decree, in particular, on the basis of the regular improvement of the pedagogical and professional level of professors of higher educational institutions, their legislative norms, theory, scientific and practical research, technological development and innovations in the taught subjects, as well as the educational process in-depth study of the latest achievements in the field of modern methods of organization is especially noted. In the field of higher education, a completely new, improved system of regular retraining of professors of higher educational institutions was introduced. In 15 basic higher educational institutions, retraining and professional development courses for the heads of higher education institutions and pedagogues were organized. About 2,700 teachers of higher educational institutions were trained in these courses. In addition, more than 11 million people regularly use the Internet in our country. Most of them are students. Currently, about 4.5 million children are studying in general education schools. It has been more than eight years since all schools have been connected to the single Ziyonet network. This network is the largest information and educational resource in the Uz domain. It contains useful and important information sources for young people, textbooks and training manuals, literature on various fields, media products, multimedia tools, and a number of interactive services used for educational purposes. For this reason, the acquisition of modern innovative pedagogy, information and communication technologies by teachers using the global Internet network, multimedia systems and distance learning methods and their active application in the educational process, the foreign teaching staff of higher educational institutions modern demands are being made, such as increasing the level of practical mastery of the language. This requires the teacher to work on himself regularly. The most important thing is that all such criteria open the door to great opportunities for educating educated, broad-minded young people in our country, and attracting students to research in the most promising directions. In particular, teachers' practical knowledge of foreign languages ensures that they are aware of international best practices and achievements in this field, and apply effective experiences to the educational process. In this regard, it should be noted that the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" is of great importance. As a result of consistently developing international cooperation in the field of higher education, six of the prestigious higher education institutions abroad, including Tashkent International University of Westminster, Turin Polytechnic University, Moscow State named after M. Lomonosov, Russian Economy named after G. Plekhanov, I Branches of Gubkin Russian University of Oil and Gas, Singapore Institute of Management Development are operating. As envisaged in the national personnel training program, it is very important to achieve the integration of all stages of education, to establish methodological and practical cooperation and exchange of information between academic lyceums, vocational colleges and higher educational institutions. is bearing fruit. At this point, it is worth noting that Uzbekistan, the first among the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, moved to a modern two-level bachelor's and master's course, which is one of the most important changes in the system. The importance of sports in making young people mature in all aspects is incomparable. During the past period, more than 1500 modern sports facilities were built at the expense of the Children's Sports Development Fund of Uzbekistan. A system of annual three-stage sports competitions ("Umid Nihollar" for schoolchildren,

"Barkamol Avlod" for lyceum and college students, "Universiade" for university students) was formed. . This makes it possible to involve hundreds of thousands of children, teenagers, young men and women in physical education and sports. Speaking of this, last year alone, 1,668 of our athletes, including 567 of our girls, participated in 165 international competitions and won 983 medals, and our young talented musicians and performers won 137 prizes in prestigious international competitions. It should be said that 76 of them were Grand Prix and first place.

In conclusion, the most important thing is that great changes have appeared in the minds of our people regarding the education system, and the desire and interest in learning has increased among our youth. Today, our talented young people are managing complex technologies in industries operating on the basis of the new, most modern requirements of our country, achieving great achievements and milestones in the fields of science, culture, and sports. Even so, this is the result of the head of state and government working in line with the times, their incomparable care for the education system, and paying special attention to the process of large-scale educational reforms. After all, the present and the future of each country are literally determined by the level of development of the educational system and the conditions created for educating the young generation.

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